

The Image of New Woman in Select Novels of Shobaa De

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 1

Month : June

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-2645

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Selvam, A and S. Thanigaivelan. "The Image of New Woman in Select Novels of Shobaa De." *Shanlax International Journal of English*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2019, pp. 34–36.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3269027>

Dr.A.Selvam, M.A., M.Phil., Ph.D.,

*Former Head & Associate Professor
NMSS Vellaichamy Nadar College, Madurai*

S.Thanigaivelan

*Ph.D. Research Scholar in English
Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai*

Abstract

The Indian English novel has witnessed a significant growth particularly over the last three decades. There is a certain multiplicity of themes and variety of styles seen in this genre today. Apart from the political and social themes, there are gender-based themes, ethnic-minority themes and themes dealing with the expatriate experience. The present paper provides a modest study of the novels of Shobaa De, the most popular Indian Woman writer in English. It has made comprehensive critical comments on her fiction with an emphasis on the image of woman portrayed in her novels. She has an extraordinary ability to discuss very sensitive aspects of human relationship in general and man-woman relationship in particular. The researcher explores and explicates the overall images of women appeared in her novels. She has portrayed a variety of women from the traditional, subjugated and marginalized to the extremely modern, liberated and emancipated women. The study focuses on the image of ne woman depicted in the novels of Shobaa De.

Keywords: Subjugation, Marginalization, Liberation, Emancipation, Marriage and Patriarchy.

Shobaa De, portrays the image of liberated and emancipated women in her novels. As a feminist, she projects the ideas of the liberating woman through self-realization and the quest for self-identity. She believes that the woman has to be aware of her own identity as a human being and should think for herself.

In *Socialite Evenings*, Karuna wants to move out of her middle-class background. Karuna's self-actualized portrayal reflects her longing to initiate and regulate her life on her own. In contrast to the weak and submissive traditional Indian woman, she is strong and courageous enough to get emancipated from the orthodox role of women. She does not need the protection and umbrella of a male partner in her day-to-day routine. Right from her childhood she is above the limiting restrictions of an individual family. Modern 'New Woman' Karuna is independent in every way. She breaks the bonds of marriage and lands her feet firm into the profession of her choice that is modeling and as an independent journalistic essayist.

Like *Socialite Evenings*, *Starry Nights*, also has the theme of liberated woman. It depicts the modern woman's struggle and search for identity. Aasha Rani comes from the south Indian middle class background. But the moment she steps in the tinsel town of Mumbai, she becomes a liberated woman who lives for her own pleasures and knows no moral codes and value system. De reinforces her plea for liberation through the example of Sudha.. Just like Aasha Rani she is modern, bold and capable enough to survive in the declining moral values of life. De describes aptly how Sudha is liberated and proud of her achievement.

Through the novel *Sisters*, Shobhaa De dives deep into the hearts of the liberated upper class women in the contemporary society and depicts the real characters as they are and not as they ought to be. Mikki and Alisha pass through the unpleasant experiences of life and how they eventually realize which is the their freedom, a freedom to live a life of their own choice. Mikki is neither shocked nor upset by the tragic death of her parents. She is a stranger even to the funeral ritual and the crowd. Being an educated, liberated young woman without any legitimate guardian to look after her, she attends many parties. Alisha is determined to smash the traditional image of woman. She indulges in free sex using men as playthings. She wants Dr. Kurien to leave his wife and children and marry her. Thus, De's women break all sorts of taboos and feel liberated. De seems to show the arrival of new women who rebel against the existing subordination and passivity of woman and "project their own passions onto others as a female power play in order to deconstruct the male ego" (Swain 135).

Shobhaa De's *Strange Obsession* is the unique creation as it depicts the lesbian relationship between two women. The idea of woman as a free and independent being is repeatedly emphasized. The story of the novel moves around the life and lesbian relationship of two young women namely Amrita Aggarwal and Meenakshi Iyengar. The protest against male hegemony takes another form in sexual matters in this novel. In *Sultry Days* Shobhaa De's skill in depicting the female characters is simply remarkable. Besides this, what is interesting to note is her treatment of the position of women and their attitude to marriage. The novelist presents a group of modern women who are the liberated and emancipated new women who highlight the changed perspectives of women in recent times. K.K. Sinha rightly says: "Shobhaa De stands for equal and normal treatment to the woman in this hurly-burly world of ours....She stands for the New Woman casual looking but ambitious professional focused and in control" (59).

Shobhaa De in *Second Thoughts* uses the city of Mumbai as a metaphor for freedom. In the beginning of the novel it is used as a rationale for the protagonist Maya's decision to accept the role of a housewife in an arranged marriage. However both the city and her marriage shatter her expectations. Maya's desire to lead a free life in the licentious set up of Mumbai is frustrated, as she fails to understand her husband's outlook. Maya begins to discover that her own position as a wife to a man who is a western-educated bank official, is undermined by his traditional attitude towards women. The world of Shobhaa De's novel *Snapshots* is entirely dominated by women. It is a world full of adventures of powerful unrestrained free new women. The writer while exploring the experiences of six women Swati, Aparna, Reema, Noor, Surekha and Rashmi, presents a very candid picture of the metropolitan lifestyle through a transformed version of the traditional values.

Shobhaa De's women characters are rebellious and new women and liberated human beings. De delves deep into the hearts of the liberated upperclass women in the contemporary society and depicts them as they are and not as what they should have been. De's novels indicate the emergence of a new woman curious to revolt against the traditional moral orthodoxy of the patriarchal social system. She tries forcefully to undo this distorted image of woman who cries for freedom and equality which is still an unheard melody in the patriarchal world.

Works Cited

1. De, Shobhaa. *Socialite Evenings*. New Delhi: Penguin Books Ltd., 1989. Print.
2. ---. *Sisters*. New Delhi: Penguin Books Ltd., 1992. Print.
3. ---. *Starry Nights*. New Delhi: Penguin Books, 1992. Print.
4. ---. *Strange Obsession*. New Delhi: Penguin Books, 1992. Print.
5. ---. *Snapshots*. New Delhi: Penguin Books Ltd., 1995. Print.
6. ---. *Second Thoughts*. New Delhi: Penguin Books, 1996. Print.
7. Swain, S. P. "ShobhaDe's *Socialite Evenings* – A Feminist Study". *Feminist English Literature*. Ed. Manmohan K. Bhatnagar. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers, 1999. Print.
8. Sinha, K. K. *The Commonwealth Review* 9.2 (1997-1998): 15. Web.